

Research

Fire and Economic Risk Assessment of Petrol Pumps within Kathmandu District

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Abstract: A Service Station is a facility, which sells fuel and lubricants for motor vehicles. The main objective of Petrol Filling Stations (PFS) is to provide fueling facilities for motor vehicles. Kathmandu District holds 102 active filling stations prone to extreme accidents and high explosion potentials. In this study, 27 out of 102 petrol pumps were investigated from the main city core area and other area. Fire risk assessment and economic loss from petrol pumps were carried out in those sampled petrol pumps by the application of the ALOHA (Areal Location of Hazardous Atmosphere) and MARPLOT software, questionnaire, and the related expert's viewpoints. Petrol Pump distribution map was prepared by using GIS model and the impact of each parameter in the probability and severity of fire in those filling stations were determined. The fire risk area, that can be affected by fire and explosion was determined, the highest area was 2.82Km² and the minimum was 0.63Km². Total economy of NPRs 53820.85 million was likely to be loss in potentially lethal zone if buildings were fully damaged. Total number of households affected by fire and explosions ranged from 410-1034 in different locations. Thus, these filling stations need to be well-prepared and planned in case of disaster like fire and earthquake. All the risky aspects must be determined beforehand to prevent catastrophic events in these pumps. Prompt and urgent improvements, as well as training to the staffs are needed in case of emergency.

Keywords: Disaster, Fire, Impacts, Urban, Vulnerability

Introduction

A Petrol Pump is the place, where fuel and lubricates is sold to the vehicles inside the region. Petrol stations contain high concentrations of highly flammable substances (Ayodele, 2011).

Fire and explosions may cause huge damage, injury and loss of human life. The main causes of petrol filling stations catching fire are sparks from a vehicle or electrical short-circuit, cigarette lighting and leakage of reservoir, earthquake and subsequent fire. Petrol pump inside the urban environment is one of the potential danger and source of disaster and vulnerable in itself (Nwanjo & Ojiako, 2007).

It may cause negative impacts like fire and explosion impacts, health and safety impacts, environmental impacts, traffic impacts and economic impacts. Beside its negative impacts, it is also serving the people in daily life and is one of the important lifelines. Hence to minimize and manage the risks associated with such pumps, an appropriate risk assessment system design should be made, so that the levels of risk would be assessed and a desired systematic controlling program would be organized. The accidents records related to petrol pump in Korea showed that 41 accidents have occurred from 1992 to 2003 and out of 41 cases, 61% were fire and explosions (Park, 2006).

Risk is the product of occurrences of a hazardous event or exposure and the severity of injury or ill health that can be cause by event or exposure. Risk assessment is the process of determining the likelihood and extent of harm caused by a technology, process or product. It involves quantitative analysis of data in order to assign a probability to the occurrence of an unwanted or harmful effect. (Ahmed, 2003)

A fire is a complex chain reaction where a fuel combines with oxygen to generate heat, smoke, and light. Most chemical fires will be trigger by one of the following ignition sources: sparks, static electricity, heat, or flames from another fire. Additionally, if a chemical is above its auto ignition temperature it will spontaneously catch on fire without an external ignition source (ALOHA, 2007).

Fire risk assessment is the assessment of the risks to the people and property because of unwanted fires. As simple Risk Assessment considers the probability of the occurrence of a certain unwanted fire scenario and the consequence of that scenario. A comprehensive risk assessment considers all probable unwanted fire scenarios and their consequences (Fowles & Silver, 2015).

Petrol is produced from crude petroleum through the distillation and refining process is known as gasoline in some countries. According to the US Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR), there are typically more than 150 chemicals in petrol, including small

amounts of benzene, toluene, xylene, ethylbenzene, and trace amounts of some contaminants, such as lead. The actual composition varies with the source of the crude petroleum, the manufacturer, and the time of year (Liccione, 1995).

Recent study by Lee et al. (2019) highlighted to propose a reasonable method to determine the safety distances with the consideration of the physicochemical characteristics and the amount of chemical substances being handled for the prevention of domino explosions (the primary explosions bringing about the secondary as well as tertiary explosions or fire with nearby flammable materials).

In this regard, the petrol discussed in this research is that mixture of petroleum-derived hydrocarbons used as fuel for engines in automobiles and other vehicles and diesel are included in this risk assessment. However, in case of Nepal there is hardly a guideline published, regarding the filling stations. Petrol has a high vapour pressure and rapidly evaporates at normal ambient temperatures. Small spills of petrol in filling stations can therefore contribute to significant air concentrations (Liccione, 1995). Diesel fuel is known to emit pollutants that have a negative impact on environmental and human health (Moolla et al., 2015).

Materials and methods

Study area

Kathmandu is the capital district of Nepal with the area of 395 km² (153 sq mi) and is the most densely populated district of Nepal with 1,744,240 populations in 2011(CBS 2011). The district is located from 27°27'E to 27°49'E longitude and 85°10'N to 85°32'N latitude. It is surrounded by Bhaktapur and Kavrepalchok District in East, Dhading and Nuwakot District in west, Nuwakot and Sindhupalchok District in North, Lalitpur and Makawanpur District in South. Figure 1 shows the detailed locations of sampled petrol pump.

Figure 1 Topographical map of Kathmandu with the locations of sampled petrol Pump or filling stations.

Data Collection

Primary data was collected from field by questionnaire survey, key Informant Interview and expert review. Secondary data collection was done by literature review of reports and journals and documents. Economic loss was calculated from the risk area of each petrol pumps. Number of households were counted and household covered area was calculated. The current average cost of the buildings was calculated according to the Department of Urban Development & Building Construction Valuation Standard. Value of per square feet was multiplied with household area in square feet and total multiplied by stories of house.

Total economy likely to be loss = No of building × Total area of per household × Cost of per Square feet

Sampling Design

Sample was taken by using stratified random sampling. Out of 102 pumps, 27 samples were selected by using random point selection method. Samples were taken from different strata. Sampling covered all types of places of Kathmandu district. Different area was selected from Kalanki, Kalimati, Tripureshowr, Balaju. Some pumps from growing city areas like Golfutar, Mulpani, Jorpati, and Kapan. Some international tools were used for the assessment of the sampled petrol pumps which are listed below:

- ALOHA- Areal Locations of Hazardous Atmospheres - (used for hazard mapping of the petrol pumps).
- MARPLOT- (Mapping Application for Response, Planning, and Local Operational tasks)
- GPS- (Global Positioning system).
- GIS- (Geographic Information System)

ALOHA can model the dispersion of a cloud of pollutant gas in the atmosphere and display a diagram that shows an overhead view of the regions, or threat zones, in which it predicts that key hazard levels (LOCs) will be exceeded. This diagram is called a threat zone plot. To obtain a threat zone estimate, we must first choose at least one LOC. For toxic gas dispersion scenarios, an LOC is a threshold concentration of the gas at ground level—usually the concentration above which a hazard is believed to exist. The type of LOC will depend on the scenario. For each LOC we choose, ALOHA estimates a threat zone where the hazard is predicted to exceed that LOC at some time after a release begins. These zones are displayed on a single threat zone plot. If three LOCs are chosen, ALOHA will display the threat zones in red, orange and yellow. When we use ALOHA's default LOCs, the red zone represents the worst hazard.

Risk and Scenario Analysis by ALOHA

Basic data fed into the ALOHA model and the assumptions (Table 1) taken for predicting the damage potential of petrol pumps are as following.

Table 1 Basic data fed in ALOHA for Mahalaxmi Fuel Center, Kathmandu

Station name	Mahalaxmi Fuel Center, Kathmandu
Location	27°41'53.3"N 85 ° 18'10.1"E
Chemical data	<i>Name: Isooctane</i> <i>Weight: 114.23g/mol</i> <i>Ambient boiling point: 97.5° C</i> <i>Vapour pressure at Ambient Temperature: 0.069 atm</i>
Atmospheric data	<i>Wind: 1.5m/s from west-south (SW) at 10-meter height during day time</i> <i>Ground roughness: Urban or forest</i> <i>Stability class: B (slightly unstable) No inversion height</i> <i>Relative humidity: 75%</i> <i>Tank diameter: 2.6 meters</i> <i>Tank volume: 96000 liters</i> <i>Chemical mass in tank: 71.8 tons</i> <i>Internal temperature: 23⁰ C</i> <i>Tank contains: Liquid</i> <i>Tank is 95% full</i>

Results and Discussion

Figure 2 Schematic plots of overlapping of risk area in (a) all sampled petrol pump, (b) Kalanki area, (c) Samakhushi (d) Balaju (e) Sundhara, (f) Kalimati (g) Jorpati and (h) Tripureshwor area.

Almost all the studied petrol pumps are surrounded by residential areas because of city enlargement. The petrol pumps, which were isolated in past, are now surrounded by houses. Demand of petroleum products is very high in the city, so the suppliers are interested to build the pumps inside city core area. Until this date there are 102 petrol pumps well operating in Kathmandu district. Study showed that many petrol pumps are built haphazardly without proper management. Fire risk area of petrol pumps was different because of the pump capacities. Smaller capacity of pump had smaller risk area and bigger capacity of pump had bigger risk area because more petrol means more fire and more explosion chemical present. Core area pump had more risk than other pumps, which covered more households. The standard distance set by Nepal Oil Corporation is 300m from one pump to another, this standard has not met at several pumps. According to the results, 447m distance was minimum to each petrol pump and it can vary according to petrol pump capacity. This standard is for 20KL Petrol Pump.

Fire risk area is higher in Pioneer fuel and Suppliers that followed by Mahalaxmi fuel Center. Pioneer fuel and Suppliers covered area of 3.87 km² and Mahalaxmi fuel Center covered area of 2.84 km². Petrol pumps with smaller area covering are Banjala Suppliers and Tapasya Traders. Area covered by Banjala Suppliers was 0.63 km² and area covered by Tapasya Traders was 0.73 km².

Risk and explosion area has proportional relationship. Risk depends on capacity of petrol pump and number of households in that area. If the risk area is larger the number of households is also higher and vice-versa. Fire may catch because of flammable nature of petrol and diesel. Fire risk can be trigger by spill and leakage. It depends on petrol pump capacity, number of buildings and risk area. Pioneer Fuel and Lubricants has high-risk area, which is because of high capacity of petrol pump i.e 100KL

Higher the number of households higher economic loss at that area. High capacity of pump has high risk area and high economic loss in comparison to smaller size pump. Economic loss was high in high risk zone (i.e. Red colored area in map) because of distance nearer to petrol pump and high pressure from fire and explosion. Second-degree burn area (i.e. orange colored area) is less risky than red colored area because of distance from pump and pressure of fire and explosion. Yellow colored area is less risky in comparison to previous two areas. Yellow colored area is far from petrol pumps and effect of fire and explosion is less. Hence, it can be conclude that if there is higher risk of fire, the economic risk is also higher and vice versa.

Risk overlapping is seen in many cases. In this research, overlapping of risk has seen in Balaju, Kalimati, Bafal, Samakhushi, Jorpati, Tripureshwor, and Bhadrakali. Figure 2 shows the details of risk overlapping inside Kathmandu district within the taken sample.

All the above overlapping examples show the results that if distance between pump is less, then overlapping is high. Kotu Dhoku and Chakrapath Oil overlapping area are higher than Ganapati Oil and Narayani Oil Store's risk overlapping area. If distance between pump is high, then chances of overlapping is less. Out of 27 sample pumps, there is condition of overlapping of risk area seen in 20 petrol pumps. This is 74.04% of sample pumps. It shows the condition of replacement of petrol pumps outside the city.

Table 2 Radial Risk Area

SN	Name	ID	Radius(m)		
			Potentially Lethal Zone	2 nd Degree Burn Zone	Low pain Zone
1	Sanjay Service Center	pp1	253	360	562
2	Sita Care Pvt Ltd	pp2	267	378	586
3	Mali Oil Stores	pp3	304	430	668
4	Jayanti Oil Stores	pp4	243	355	553
5	Maya Ram Bhola Ram	pp5	270	384	598
6	National Treading Oil Store	pp6	357	505	783
7	Pioneer Fuel and Lubricates	pp7	505	714	1110
8	Sita Fuel pvt.ltd	pp8	281	397	627
9	Khadka Oil Pvt.Ltd	pp9	383	541	841
10	Nilbarahi Petrol Pump	pp10	283	401	626
11	Jubi Enterprises	pp11	281	399	622
12	Baba Oil pvt.ltd	pp12	281	400	624
13	Narayani Oil Center	pp13	249	355	554
14	Ganapati Oil Tread Link	pp14	264	376	585
15	Jay Kumari Interprises	pp15	233	333	520
16	Kotu Dhuku Oil Store	pp16	249	355	553
17	Harisiddhi Oil Store	pp17	293	416	646
18	Chakrapath Fuel Center	pp18	249	355	553
19	Aakash Jogini Enterprises	pp19	357	504	786
20	Rakastar Treading	pp20	249	355	553
21	Bhadra Fuel Concern	pp21	216	308	482
22	Tapasya Treders	pp22	251	359	560
23	Ripu Mardini	pp23	305	432	670
24	New Lama Enterprises	pp24	339	478	742
25	Kathmandu Oil Store	pp25	374	527	817
26	Banjala Suppelires	pp26	199	285	447
27	Mahalaxmi Fuel center	pp27	436	613	947

Table 3 Household and Estimated Economy loss

SN	Name	ID	Household no			Total no of Households	Grand Total in Million(Rs)
			Potentially Lethal Zone	2 nd Degree Burn Zone	Low pain Zone		
1	Sanjay Service	pp1	62	172	380	614	2945.25
2	Sita Care Pvt Ltd	pp2	110	242	410	762	2244
3	Mali Oil Stores	pp3	320	190	320	830	1040.18
4	Jayanti Oil Stores	pp4	152	168	458	778	911.62
5	Maya Ram Bhola Ram	pp5	150	152	432	734	1250.56
6	National Treading Oil Store	pp6	282	322	387	991	2395.93
7	Pioneer Fuel and Lubricates	pp7	232	242	352	826	3798.44
8	Sita Fuel pvt.ltd	pp8	220	350	389	959	958.37
9	Khadka Oil Pvt.Ltd	pp9	198	220	382	800	1776.5
10	Nilbarahi Petrol Pump	pp10	108	132	340	580	841.5
11	Jubi Enterprises	pp11	72	72	389	533	2127.12
12	Baba Oil pvt.ltd	pp12	192	218	356	766	2314.12
13	Narayani Oil Center	pp13	238	148	289	675	2454.37
14	Ganapati Oil Tread Link	pp14	205	290	198	693	2711.5
15	Jay Kumari Interprises	pp15	82	132	340	554	3740
16	Kotu Dhuku Oil Store	pp16	210	222	427	859	1753.12
17	Harisiddhi Oil Store	pp17	325	281	320	926	2781.62
18	Chakrapath Fuel Center	pp18	107	210	267	584	3295.87
19	Aakash Jogini Enterprises	pp19	252	192	242	686	1659.62
20	Rakastar Treading	pp20	73	110	432	615	1262.25
21	Bhadra Fuel Concern	pp21	78	117	215	410	3623.12
22	Tapasya Treders	pp22	162	220	380	762	853.18
23	Ripu Mardini	pp23	52	160	460	672	607.75
24	New Lama Enterprises	pp24	142	120	429	691	724.62
25	Kathmandu Oil Store	pp25	182	140	421	743	1285.62
26	Banjala Suppelires	pp26	89	134	280	503	2571.25
27	Mahalaxmi Fuel center	pp27	310	340	384	1034	1893.37

Conclusion

Petrol Pump distribution map was prepared and most of the petrol pumps were located in City core area according to Google map. Through this research, it concludes that, Kathamandu district is risky in terms of fire and explosion. Because of high density of houses and low distance between pumps and its surrounding buildings and high degree of overlapping of risk area. Fire risk area of petrol pump was determined and plotted in Google street map. Economy likely to be loss from pump was calculated. Rs 53820.85 million was the total loss from petrol pumps within highly risky zone i.e potentially lethal zone (red zone). The government should do risk assessment of petrol pumps and vulnerability analysis. Safety measure and distance between petrol pumps should maintain otherwise, it should shift from city core area to outside the city. There is need for more research related to filling station especially issues related to site selection and optimization. In addition, issue like people's perception on the location of the filling station can be investigate. Minimum distance between petrol pumps allocated by NOC should be changed according to capacity of petrol pump.

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Conflicts of Interest

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